

Perspective-based specification of machine learning-enabled systems

Dear Participant,

Thank you very much for taking 5 minutes of your valuable time to answer this questionnaire.

Objective: We are interested in knowing your experiences with the development of systems based on Machine Learning (ML) to understand how our proposal helps to face one of the main challenges in this context: the specification of requirements for systems based on ML.

For more information/questions, contact:

Author 2 - email@domain
 Author 1 - email@domain
 University related to the authors

[Redacted] (not shared) [Switch account](#)

* Required

Name *

Your answer

What is your highest level of education?

Choose

What is your background?

It is possible to enter more than one.

Your answer

How many years of experience do you have with software development in general? *

Your answer

How many years of experience do you have developing/managing systems involving ML? *

Your answer

How many systems development projects involving ML have you participated in? *

Your answer

Perspective-based ML concerns and tasks diagram

The diagram below has been used to provide an overview of ML concerns and tasks for those involved in the design and development of the ML-enabled system.

Specification template based on perspectives of ML-enabled systems

The template below summarizes the perspective-based ML concerns and tasks diagram. The template was used to partially specify two challenges involving ML components of the Innovation initiative. In the link below you can find the artifacts generated for each challenge.

P.S. Please consider the perspective-based ML concerns and tasks diagram and the artifacts generated to answer the questionnaire questions.

How do you perceive the relevance of each of the perspectives? *

	Little relevant	Reasonably relevant	Relevant	Very relevant
ML objectives	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
User Experience	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Model	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

In your opinion, are the concerns of each perspective complete? *

	No	Yes
ML objectives	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
User Experience	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Model	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

For the perspectives that you rated "No" in the previous question, please indicate unaddressed concerns.

Your answer

In your opinion, does using the perspective-based ML concerns and tasks diagram **help to identify important requirements** that would be missed or identified late without using the approach? *

- No
- Yes

In your opinion, does the specification template **make the concerns easier to understand and provide a clear description** of the ML-enabled system? *

- No
- Yes

Regarding your perception of the ease of use, usefulness and intention to use the **approach (diagram + template)**, how much do you agree with the following statements:

	Strongly disagree	Partially disagree	Partially agree	Strongly agree
I found the approach easy to use	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Using the approach would be useful to support more complete and accurate specification of ML-based system requirements.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I would use the approach to specify ML-based system requirements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Do you have any other suggestions for improvements to the perspectives, concerns, diagram or template?

Your answer

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